

The Organizing Committee of
20th SDEWES Conference
FMENA, University of Zagreb
Ivana Lučića 5
HR-10000 Zagreb
CROATIA

To:
Mr. Patrick Mack
TH Köln,
50679 Köln,
Germany

This letter confirms that **Mr. Patrick Mack** has the following submissions reviewed by the editors and accepted for presentation and publication on digital proceedings of the 20 SDEWES Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems to be held from October 5 - 10, 2025 in Dubrovnik, Croatia:

Oral presentation(s)

SDEWES2025-0113 Physics-Aware Validation of State Estimations for electrical Power Grids based on Artificial Neural Networks

by Patrick Mack*, Markus De Koster, Patrick Lehnen, Eberhard Waffenschmidt, Ingo Stadler

SDEWES2025-0354 Synthetic Topology Generation for Generalizable Machine Learning in Low Voltage Distribution Grids

by Markus De Koster*, Patrick Lehnen, Patrick Mack, Eberhard Waffenschmidt, Ingo Stadler

The oral presentations will be conducted in the 15 minutes presentation plus 5 minutes discussion fashion.

This letter DOES NOT serve for getting entry visa to Croatia!

For any communication please use the following e-mail address: sdewes2025@sdewes.org

Sincerely yours,

Prof. Neven Duić
Chairman of Local Organizing Committee